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The Ascendancy of Political Imagination: A Spectacular View of the Literary Field

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Abstract:

There is a unique and specific steel link between politics and literature. They both may seem to be two significant and integral parts of the human experience. This study explores the complex relationship between politics and literature. It emphasizes the idea that politics as well as literature has an equal extent of power to amend each other, that is, the political scenario has the capacity to reform and modify the composition of literature. Literary pieces can criticize, alter, and revolutionize the political understandings and beliefs of the community as a whole. Thus, this study is an attempt to apprehend and recognize the political features of literature and disclose the political propensity in the composition of literature. This study came out of curiosity to investigate the lasting effect of the political affairs people have on their minds and the study seeks to identify the impact of history on an individual's fate, human life, and psyche, and even literature.

Keywords: Politics, Political Literature, Political imagination, Political consciousness, Political identity, History.

Introduction

Politics and literature can be seen as two facets, intertwined. Both aspects are related to human experience and are reconcilable. While literature is a mirror of society, it reflects the aspirations and ambitions of the nation of a particular period. It is a historic document and an expression of the life of the nation or a society. Politics is related to the government, the institutional power that decides how the nation will be governed. It gives insight into the social background and the political structure of the place. Politics is even related to history, which is also a significant element of literature. The relation between politics and literature is a very important point that is needed to understand the notion of politics in any literary work. Politics had a profound impact on literature. The political situation of the age and place inspired and forced many writers to write on the social issues of society, and literature became a medium to raise their voice for the sake of mankind. The other way round, literature also influenced the political scenario. Many political works paved the way for many movements that helped in eradicating the ills of society. Both aspects are inseparable. “The relationship between literature and politics is a multilane freeway with traffic flowing freely in both directions: Any work of literature is in part a product of sociological and political factors, to the extent that the writer's personality has been shaped by the sociological and political environment of his time. Conversely, important works of literature or whole movements have had profound effects on society by setting up or destroying taboos, conventions, and social prejudices, thus contributing to changes in values which in turn have brought about social and political change” (Lindberg 1). There is appreciable political literature which are concerned with ideologies, like Capitalism, Socialism, Marxism, Nazism, etc., written by great philosophers with the intention to bring change in the political system. Political events, whether they are related to the government, or a war against an enemy, or to cast away colonialism of territory and mind, are concerned with decisive moments in the lives of people, as well as challenges which display

the will of the people to fight for a blissful life and future. All the classes of people are wrapped around these crucial political events. It cannot be declared untrue that politics and literature have a deep connection from the way before, as both fields are a source of ideas and imagination and have become a tool for one another. About the relationship between politics and literature, the statement of an Italian writer and journalist, Italo Calvino, from *The Uses of Literature*, is worth quoting here. He says,

“Literature is necessary to politics above when it gives a voice to the one who doesn’t have a voice, when it gives a name, and especially to all that political language excludes or tends to exclude...Literature is like an ear that can hear more than politics; Literature is like an eye that can perceive beyond the chromatic scale to which politics is sensitive.” (98)

The writer here opines two propositions; the first is that literature is important to politics, as it gives voice to the voiceless. It becomes the medium to express. The second proposition he gives is related to perception. He says, literature is like an “ear” and “eye” that sees and hears more than the literature. There is a sense of superiority regarding literature. He gives more importance to literature. Literature plays a crucial role by providing aid to explore and analyze the political ideas and social issues. Through the use of fictional narratives, characters, and diction, literature presents a clear image of society, and it gives a deep understanding of the political events and ideologies. Furthermore, literature acts as a source of solutions to address and tackle the existing or future social and political problems. For instance, George Orwell’s *Animal Farm* is a political satire where the author uses the flock of animals to address the hazards of totalitarianism. The novel displays the result of permitting a group of leaders to lead, who become absolute and dominate the society. The work criticizes the political ideology of totalitarianism. Even taking into consideration his other dystopian novel, *1984*, which gives the readers insight into what the result would be of allowing ‘the party’ to have complete control. The way the governing body becomes overpowering and makes the lives of

the people ‘a great suffering’. These instances illustrate how literature helps in analyzing political ideologies.

Politics and Literature

Politics is not limited to the government, rules, and policies it implements; rather, it expands its boundaries concerning real-life effects on society. It includes diverse opinions of the people whose lives are directly and indirectly affected by the political structure. For anyone, being political does not mean remaining confined to government and its organs. Being neutral about the incidents that one sees and listens to is tough. The relationship between politics and literature is like the wind interacting with a person. Political literature uses stories to make statements and criticize the political events, system, and theories. Political novels directly do this, criticizing the ills and making people conscious about the sufferings of humanity around the world. Politics has always been a captivating theme for literature, not from today but way before, the earliest of the civilizations, from Plato’s *Republic* written in 380 BC to the twenty-first century. Philosophers and writers like Aristophanes, Plato, Thomas More, Jonathan Swift, Voltaire, Charles Dickens, Leo Tolstoy, Joseph Conrad, and George Orwell were free to express their opinions and to present their thoughts before the eyes of society.

Political literature is a literary work, specifically a novel; however, plays and poetry can also be considered as a part of this genre. It emphasizes criticizing society and politics. There is a depiction of the social and political structure, and also the portrayal of the state of tenseness arising. The political novel is closely associated with the historical novel, social novel, proletarian novel, and social science fiction. The genre can be based on the political events of the past or of the present. The narrative of interest to politics can be metaphorical, satirical, or allegorical, and it conveys the fundamental message. In the emergence and development of political literature, the social system of the place played a crucial role, but politics as a theme in writing was present from the beginning of human civilization.

Starting from ancient Greek literature, where Aristophanes wrote his famous social and political writing, *The Knights*. In ancient times, Greece was divided into two parts: Athens and Sparta. The city-state concept, which is a part of political science, came from ancient Greek civilization. Aristophanes wrote the satire to criticize the general of Athens, Cleon. Plato's *Republic* is a Socratic dialogue and is his most renowned work, written in 380 B.C., which is concerned with the state and justice and gives the concept of the 'ideal state'. It has two titles, the first is the 'Republic', which means 'politeia' in Greek and 'constitution of state' in English. The second title is 'concerning justice'. He gives an idea of how an ideal state should be and how good governance can bring prosperity to the state and happiness to the lives of the people. For him, justice is something moral. It is not mere strength, but it is a harmonious strength. The medieval period was the time of rise and decline of one of the biggest empires the world has ever seen, and that was the Roman Empire. Also known as the 'Dark Age', it was a highly religious era. The political thought of the time was the relationship between the state and the church. Niccolo Machiavelli's *The Prince* became the spark in the Renaissance movement. He was the first political thinker who attempted to separate politics from religion. In the text, he gives his view on human nature, talks about the characteristics of the ruler, and the government.

Thomas More's *Utopia*, written in 1516, is a socio-political satire. In which More creates an imaginary state that is perfect and has no flaws. There, he constitutes a fictional island and community living with no differences; all the people share the same beliefs, customs, and way of living. More wrote to bring change in European society, introducing a blissful world that can exist. The seventeenth-century Britain had a two-party system, the Tories and the Whigs. Both the political parties were indulging in a war. The conservative Tory party was the supporter of the monarchs, while the Whigs were the promoters of the parliament. The political conflict of the era was penned by major writers of the age. John Dryden, the best-known satirist, wrote his most famous poem, *Absalom and Achitophel*. The poem consists of the biblical story

of Absalom and his rebellion against his father, who was the king as well, which also represents the contemporary society of John Dryden. The political satire might be written against King Charles II, who fled to France, and the monarchy was restored under his rule in England.

The Puritans, also known as English protestants, conflicted with the monarchs, opposing the political authority over the Church. *Hudibras* by Samuel Butler is a satire on the Puritans, and the popularity of the book struck a chord with the then-current political and religious conflict. Thomas Hobbes' *Leviathan* is a work composed during the English Civil War. It deals with the structure of the state, the legitimate form of government, and social contract theory (the contract is made between the people of the society so that they can live peacefully). The Civil War might have influenced his thought, and so he opines that the state has a savage nature and should be governed by a strong government. In the eighteenth century, the world experienced many political events. The Industrial Revolution started in the middle of the 18th century and was responsible for many changes in society. The rule of King Louis XVI in France led to the French Revolution, the revolt moulded the world in different directions, thinking about and emphasizing liberty, equality among different classes of society, and fraternity of the people. There were tremendous political changes that Europe and the whole world were experiencing at that time, including America, Africa, Asia, and many other nations.

Many writers, political thinkers, philosophers, theorists, and even poets come up with their works to address such events and the changes they brought. Jean Jacques Rousseau's *The Social Contract* became the basis of many reforms and revolts in Europe. The book presents the idea against the 'divinity of the monarchs. He rejects the concept that kings and queens have divine power to rule; rather, the power rests in the hands of the people. The concept of the Social Contract Theory came into existence and developed to be more popular during the sixteenth century. Political theorists like Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, and Jean Jacques

Rousseau were the eminent promoters. Alexander Pope's *The Rape of the Lock*, published in the year 1712, includes the high qualities of the heroic epic. It is a form of Horatian satire, and the writer mocks the manner of society. He presents the actions of the people of higher strata as ridiculous and foolish, with no sense. The poet here does not directly criticize contemporary society; rather, he brings laughter through the characters. It is a gentle satire. Jonathan Swift's *A Modest Proposal* is an example of the Juvenalian form of satire. In Total contrast to Pope, Swift here bitterly talks about the extent of British Colonialism concerning Ireland. The work features direct, harsh, biting, and critical of the vices and follies of society. Jonathan Swift's *Gulliver's Travels*, published in 1726, became the medium to shed light on the ills of the political system of Britain. The 'rope dance' reflects the corruption, the 'low heels' and 'high heels', and the division in the party. He criticizes the uncertainties of politics. The French philosopher Voltaire's *Candide* is another classic example where he questions the role of government. on individualism, and the happiness of the people became a priority.

The political novel is a recently originated genre and one of the distinctive developments in the literary field. It emerged in the first half of the nineteenth century. The age was the most suitable period for its development, and there were certain reasons behind it, partly because of the middle-class people and their struggles, partly because of the people becoming more interested in reading and conscious about the political impact they had on their lives. The novel became a weapon in the hands of the writers to paint the true picture of Victorian society. The political genre developed more in the latter half of the nineteenth century. The Victorian era is marked by many social, economic, and political changes that helped improve the education system, health, and eradicate poverty. Due to different reforms, the era witnessed the end of slavery. The Union Act gave rights in the hands of the working class in the factories. Child rights were one of the major reforms of the time that limited the exploitation of children at the workplace, and the focus was on mandatory schooling. The Adult

Franchise directed the world towards democracy and enabled people to become more conscious about their rights, and political system, and its impact.

Writers like Charles Dickens, George Eliot, Jane Austen, and John Stuart Mill used their genius and pen to write many works and brought oppression, poverty, class inequality, and exploitation of children and women in Victorian society into the spotlight. Dickens' novels include almost all the issues of the age, and he wrote for every section of society. His most famous work, which remains popular for many ages and even today that is *Oliver Twist*. Its dominant theme is child exploitation and can even be seen portraying the suffering and exploitation of women in male male-dominant society; he did that through the female characters, 'Nancy', 'Rose', and the mother of Oliver, 'Agnes'. The main character of Oliver depicts the condition of illegitimate children and the oppression they had to face in the workplace. This work became the medium for social and economic criticism and also a call for strict reforms.

His other work, *Hard Times*, is a critique of industrialization and the impact it had on society, mainly a bad impact. Dickens opines that in the modern world, due to the increase in use of technology, people have become cruel and without emotions, compassion, and imagination; life would become full of suffering; unendurable. *The Great Expectations* was written to illustrate the social and political problems of the nineteenth century. There are cluster of events happening. Dickens displayed those issues that he felt needed to be changed, such as corruption, class differences, and the rigidity of the higher class. Just like Dickens, George Eliot was also a courageous writer whose work *Mill on the Floss* paints the picture of the stereotypes of Victorian society regarding women. *On the Subjection of Women* by John Stuart Mill, the literary prose writing became the precursor of women's rights in the nineteenth century. Mill advocates for social equality between men and women. Benjamin Disraeli, the politician, writer who even served Great Britain as a Prime Minister, wrote the novel

Coningsby. The first political novel of the trilogy was published in 1844. The novel is based on real incidents happening in England, i.e., the Reform Act of 1832 and the decline of the Whig ministry of Lord Melbourne. Also, the dismemberment of Disraeli from the cabinet of Robert Peel is one such personal incident that forced him to write the novel. He wrote this novel in praise of the political group popularly known as the 'Young England'. In the twentieth-century modern world, the political literature also became modern and advanced. The themes like the government's use of technology, machines, and different forms of ideology of government ideology became prevalent. George Orwell's *1984* and Aldous Huxley's *Brave New World* is a first-rate example of politics blended with technology. In the novel *1984*, the party(government) led by a 'Big Brother' uses digital gadgets like telescreens and microphones to spy on the citizens so that they cannot violate the rules made and imposed on the society. The statement "Big brother is watching you" gives knowledge of the dominance of the government through technology. 'Room 101' stands for fear, a room where punishments are given to people who don't comply with the government. The novel *Nostramo* by Joseph Conrad is the strongest and most influential work. The work has incorporated all the themes that a perfect political work should have, i.e., rebellion, politics, power, capitalism, imperialism, conflicts, corruption, etc. The twentieth century was not the age of dictatorship; rather, democracy emerged as the most popular form of government. Hence, the rise and fall of the fictional dictator Willie Stark can be seen in the novel of Robert Penn Warren's novel *All the King's Men*. The work is all about politics and how the great politicians do it. The moral responsibility of the leader is that all his actions should be for the good of the people, but in the novel, politics becomes a means of gaining power and serving self-interest. The literature of the modern and the post-modern world was not confined to Europe; rather, the world moved on from the point when the literary field had the influence of a few countries only, and therefore it is called 'world literature'.

In the Indian context, politics is present in the core of religion, culture, and tradition. It is rooted deep in ancient religious writings, i.e., *the Vedas*, and also in the great epics of Hindu mythology, *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata*. Indian philosophy presents how the proper political system should be in order to establish peace, the rule of law, justice, and prosperity in the state. Also, great emphasis is on the ruler; his every action should be according to the 'Dharma'. The whole Indian political philosophy is based on two constructs, the first is 'dharma', the conscience of taking the right decisions for the betterment of the people, keeping away all the emotional thoughts. And the second, to establish discipline and to ensure justice, the punishment for the wrongdoings, i.e., what is called in Hindi 'danda'.

In *Ramayana*, there is a description of 'Ramrajya'. The specific vocabulary is termed with regard to the arrival of Lord Rama in Ayodhya after the exile and his ascending the throne, and hence thereafter the ideal state gets established, where there is a rule of law. In another great epic *Mahabharata*, where the politics between Kauravas and Pandavas and the diplomacy of Lord Krishna to remove evil from the earth and restoration of 'dharma' is evident.

Shanti Parv twelfth book of the epic *Mahabharata*. It is a Sanskrit word; when translated into English, it means 'Book of Peace'. The book deals with good governance. The setting of the work is after 'Dharmayuddha', between the Kauravas and Pandavas ended, and the rule of Yudhishtira started on the side of the Pandavas. It tells the characteristics of the ruler that he should be good at governing, decisive, and moral. The book is based on the words of Bhishma and ancient Saints. Chanakya's *Artha Shastra* is an ancient book that deals with the art of ruling and politics, economy, and military strategy. The author gives the idea that during the period of crisis in the state, whether at the time of natural calamities or when the state is at war, the king should make a strategy and tackle the situation. Chanakya suggests that kings should initiate public projects during times of emergency. The word 'Artha Shastra' is a Sanskrit term; when translated into English, it means 'Political Science'.

The twenty-first century is the world of digital media. People are much more aware of their surroundings; now they are not dependent on literary figures to make them familiar with the important issues and their impact. The globalized world has become so fast-forwarded that any event happening in any corner of the world spreads throughout the globe within a wink of an eye. Political thinking has also become global. As of now, people are talking about ‘Geopolitics’, the concept which deals with the ‘geography and economy’ affecting politics, and also the relation between the nations. The world is progressing towards the Digital Humanities, the intersection of the digital world and the Arts. Digital media has become a part of people's lives. It affects every aspect of life, and therefore, the arts cannot be deprived of their impact.

The imagination is related to the writer's innovative capacity, and if the imagination is political, it becomes the route to go beyond the political reality and does not change the views, beliefs, attitude, actions, or perceptions in accordance with the group they want to become part of or already belong to. In other words, “Political Imagination is a concept to designate all those imaginative processes by which collective life is symbolically experienced and this experience mobilized in view of achieving political aims.” The definition includes four key points to focus on. First is the “Imaginative process,” which refers to thinking, the evolution of new ideas. The second key point is the “Collective Life”, which means all facets of life that are the result of people's actions, i.e., living, working, and being together, in society. Next comes the “Symbolic Experience,” referring to a construct in which there is an erection of imaginative experience by making use of symbols, images, and diction, etc. The last point is the “Political Aims”. The vocabulary is commonly understood and associated with the acquisition of power, but here it refers to the common issues of the people, as well as to keep guard over social groups. The political imagination is the product of the political consciousness of the writer. It's the awakening and awareness of the political system and the realization of one's role and

position in politics. It is the aroused state of mind. 'The state of mind is based on the personal awareness of politics, position in the political system and history, and actions one perceives as available to take in an effort to influence the political reality in which one operates'. The better knowledge of the relationship between people and government, and the whole social and political scenario of the age, helps one to think sublime.

The political consciousness is deeply related to other political concepts such as participation, culture, and identity. The meaning of the term political participation is very broad. In the modern democratic era, adult franchise has become an old-fashioned thought, and it no longer remains the only way to actively participate in politics. As of now, meaning has gone beyond. To be a part of decision-making or to influence the group responsible for policy making, and to sway the entire political organization, has now been added to the meaning and definition of political participation.

Political culture is a newly developed concept. It is a mixture of the culture and politics of a particular society. For instance, the constitution of Britain is partially written and based on culture and traditions. For understanding the concept of political culture, the understanding of political values like liberty and, rule of law of a particular place becomes important. If there are fewer values, there will be less political culture, and if there are more values, then the political culture is richer. This concept is a result of political modernization. The set of internal feelings of the subject about the political system is the center of the construct; it does not give information about the events happening in the political world, rather it illustrates the thoughts, faith, and feelings of the people regarding any specific political happening. It is dynamic, inclined towards moral, ethical values, and is an expression of abstract forms. The foundation of political culture is history, geography, social and economic development, ideologies and attitudes, religion, and national symbols. History is the foremost basis of political culture. The new generation of society takes the knowledge of its political culture from the older generation,

and this concept, of any nation or any society, is deeply rooted in history. “The political aspect crops up again in cultural history.” (Goff 09)

Political Identity is more of people’s opinion about themselves in relation to politics and government of a country, and it gives assistance to the critical analysis of political systems and culture. The concept is a coalition of two ‘politics and ‘identity’, and both are interlaced in such a way that politics affects the identity and the sense of self, the identity affects the politics, and this concept sometimes becomes the cause of many movements and revolutions. The concept is as dynamic as political culture; it keeps on developing in individuals over time and is based on race, gender, caste, religion, social class, nationality, sexual orientation, and social background. Literature demonstrates that how, prior judgement, interests of the people, power and interrelationship affect the behavior of people as an individual and in group in the political domain; and also agrees to the point that political identity is a type of social identity that flecks the affiliation of definite groups sharing similar thought, beliefs and struggle for a definite form of authority.

History lends background to political imagination. History is yore politics, and the future of world politics depends on it. Historical events cavernous effect on society, and so can be seen in the works of the author, urging for change. Literature gives insight into the society and its people of a particular age, the way they behaved, the kind of attitude, beliefs, and values they had, and the writer’s insurgency against the ills, setting conventions of the tightly knit community; Art painting the history. “Writing history with skill and verve is not a distasteful exercise. Instead, it can inspire young minds, advance new and provocative ways of thinking about the world, and assist in the production of that which may approach true literature” (Snell). The study in every field begins with history and proceeds with development. When elements of history become the basis of any literary work, it furnishes; it acts as a primal matter. Imagining history through a political lens provides assistance in a deep understanding of the

struggle of mankind and the changes over time, making it the foundation for historical and political pieces of work. “With imagination applied to deep knowledge, we can establish the real choices that people had in the past, rather than anachronistic, moralistic, or wishful ones” (Axtell 457). A political work with an inclusion of history can reawaken the past memories, give new energy or strength to the bygone politics and history at the same time, and transform the literary genre; it can do so much for the good of society and can be accepted globally and well-liked on a magnificent scale. “When all the elements of style have received the necessary attention, the well-written history, like all good literature, should be a book that can be satisfactorily read aloud. If it cannot, it should be passed once more through the writer’s imagination” (462).

Conclusion

Reading history has rich reaping benefits that enhance political intelligence, leading to shaping good citizens with morals and values. Moreover, contributing to the reader’s personal growth by crafting their opinions, making it lavish and well-researched, and loaded with facts, eventually aiding in decision-making. Every human being who lives, speaks, wears, is cultured, and has faith in religion is a product of the past. Various and distinct religions, societies, cultures, and traditions are the endowment of history, and going through it always transforms to a substantial extent. But, often seen as monotonous, unrelieved, unimaginative, and dull. When assimilated with desirable narratives becomes incompetent to do any other work. This specific research divulges and traces the origin, development, and advancement of the political literature and the phenomenon that contributed to the state of flourishing of such literature.

The study proves that History can be a good political imagination coming out of political consciousness. Also, shed light on the elements that history in political works reflects, that is, the sense of identity, understanding of the world, changes that transformed the cultures, and how the present-day politics takes its base in former times. Writers have adopted historical

elements for the sake of making the literary piece more appealing. Almost all the historical events have offered the right set of circumstances to create literature that is worth reading and worth remembering. And for this reason, history touched art and literature like every other aspect of human life.

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